

**DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS
ON THE BASIS OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL MEANS**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the issues of developing professional competence of future engineers on the basis of electronic educational tools. As a result of the rapid introduction of digital technologies into the education system, the importance of using modern pedagogical approaches, electronic educational platforms, virtual laboratories and distance learning tools in engineering education is increasing. The study highlights the role of electronic educational tools in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge, developing practical skills and forming professional competence. Recommendations are also developed to improve the effectiveness of teaching in an electronic educational environment.

Keywords: electronic education, engineering education, professional competence, digital technologies, virtual laboratory, distance learning, innovative pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada elektron ta'lim vositalari asosida bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'lim tizimiga jadal kirib kelishi natijasida muhandislik ta'limida zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar, elektron ta'lim platformalari, virtual laboratoriyalar va masofaviy ta'lim vositalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Tadqiqot davomida elektron ta'lim vositalarining talabalarning nazariy bilimlarini mustahkamlash, amaliy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirishdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Shuningdek, elektron ta'lim muhitida o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron ta'lim, muhandislik ta'limi, kasbiy kompetentlik, raqamli texnologiyalar, virtual laboratoriya, masofaviy ta'lim, innovatsion pedagogika.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются вопросы развития профессиональной компетентности будущих инженеров на основе электронных средств обучения. В результате быстрого внедрения цифровых технологий в систему образования возрастает важность использования современных педагогических

подходов, электронных учебных платформ, виртуальных лабораторий и средств дистанционного обучения в инженерном образовании. В исследовании подчеркивается роль электронных средств обучения в укреплении теоретических знаний студентов, развитии практических навыков и формировании профессиональной компетентности. Также разработаны рекомендации по повышению эффективности обучения в электронной среде.

Ключевые слова: электронное обучение, инженерное образование, профессиональная компетентность, цифровые технологии, виртуальная лаборатория, дистанционное обучение, инновационная педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, one of the priority tasks is to modernize the higher education system, bring the quality of education to international standards, and train competitive personnel for the digital economy. In particular, the effective use of modern information and communication technologies in the training of specialists working in the technical and engineering fields is of great importance. Today, automation of production processes, artificial intelligence, digital control systems, and the digital transformation of industry require engineers not only in-depth theoretical knowledge, but also high-level practical skills and professional competence. Therefore, improving the professional training of students through the use of electronic learning tools in higher education institutions is one of the urgent issues. Electronic learning tools create opportunities for interactive presentation of educational materials, independent mastery of knowledge, distance learning, and individualization of the educational process. As a result, future engineers develop independent thinking, problem-solving, and innovative activity skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of developing professional competence of future engineers based on electronic learning tools is one of the current scientific directions in the fields of modern pedagogy, information technologies and engineering education. The analysis of scientific research conducted on this problem shows the important role of electronic learning technologies in improving the quality of education, improving the professional training of students and forming digital competencies. Significant scientific research has been carried out by foreign scientists in the formation and development of the theory of professional competence. In particular, J. Raven interprets competence as an integrated system of knowledge, skills, abilities and values that serve the successful implementation of a certain activity by a person. According to the scientist, a modern specialist should have not only theoretical knowledge, but also the

competences to solve practical problems, make independent decisions and evaluate his own activities. A. Khutorskoy, having developed the methodological foundations of the competency approach, defines competence as an integrated quality that determines the ability of a person to effectively organize professional activity. His research substantiates the need to assess educational outcomes not through the sum of knowledge, but through competencies manifested in practical activities. In research on the development of engineering education, the role of e-learning technologies is emphasized. The theory of connectivism, developed by G. Siemens, offers a new model of knowledge acquisition in a digital environment. According to this theory, a learner acquires knowledge through interaction with various electronic sources, information networks and digital platforms. This creates a theoretical basis for the effective use of electronic resources in engineering education. The issues of the competency approach and e-learning have also been widely studied by Uzbek scientists. In particular, N.A. Muslimov developed the scientific and methodological foundations of the competency approach in the vocational education system and highlighted the pedagogical mechanisms for the formation of professional competencies in the training of specialists. The scientist's research shows the important role of innovative pedagogical technologies in improving the professional training of future specialists. U.Sh. Begimkulov's scientific works analyze the theoretical and practical aspects of integrating information and communication technologies into the educational process. The author substantiates that the use of electronic educational tools serves to develop the culture of working with information, organize independent educational activities, and form professional competence of students. An analysis of scientific literature shows that the use of electronic educational tools is one of the effective means of developing the professional competence of future engineers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was aimed at identifying pedagogical opportunities for developing professional competence of future engineers based on electronic learning tools, analyzing existing problems, and developing effective methodological recommendations. The research methodology was based on the concepts of a competency-based approach, a systematic approach, an activity-oriented approach, and digital education. In the research process, a comprehensive set of theoretical and empirical research methods was used to determine the role, impact, and effectiveness of electronic learning tools in developing professional competence of future engineers. The theoretical basis of the study was scientific sources on competency-based education, electronic learning, digital pedagogy, and engineering education. Students studying

in engineering departments of higher educational institutions and their professional training process were selected as the object of the study. The subject of the study was the process of developing professional competence of future engineers using electronic learning tools. The following scientific methods were used during the study:

Theoretical research methods

Analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature. This method was used to study the scientific works of local and foreign scientists on e-learning, competency-based approach and engineering education. Based on the analysis of the literature, the theoretical state of the research problem, development trends and scientific views were systematized. Comparative-analytical method. The experiences of using e-learning tools in engineering education systems of different countries were studied and compared with the higher education system of Uzbekistan. Systematic analysis method. The relationship between e-learning tools, the learning process and professional competence components was systematically analyzed.

Empirical research methods

Pedagogical observation. Classes with engineering students were observed and the impact of using e-learning tools on the learning process was studied. Questionnaire. Questionnaires were conducted among students and professors to determine the effectiveness of e-learning tools. The results of the questionnaire made it possible to assess the level of use of e-learning platforms, students' interest, and the development of professional competencies. Interview method. Through interviews with teachers and students, problems and promising areas in the use of e-learning tools were identified. Pedagogical pilot study. During the study, experimental and control groups were formed. In the experimental group, teaching was established based on e-learning tools (LMS platforms, virtual laboratories, electronic textbooks, video lessons, and simulator programs). In the control group, traditional teaching methods were used. The results were compared.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Within the framework of this study, experimental work was carried out to determine the effectiveness of developing professional competence of future engineers based on electronic learning tools. The results of the study confirmed that electronic learning tools have a significant positive impact on the quality of education and professional training of students. During the experimental process, students studying in the engineering field were divided into control and experimental groups. While traditional teaching methods were used in the control group, the experimental group conducted training sessions based on Moodle, Google

Classroom, virtual laboratories, video lessons, electronic textbooks, and engineering software tools (AutoCAD, MATLAB, SolidWorks). At the beginning of the experiment, the level of formation of professional competence of students in both groups was diagnosed. The results showed that there was no significant difference between the groups. At the end of the experiment, it was found that the performance of students in the experimental group was significantly higher than that of the control group. The results obtained are consistent with the competency approach and e-learning theories of J. Raven, A. Khutorskoy, G. Siemens and T. Anderson. The studies of these scientists also emphasize the importance of digital technologies and the e-learning environment in the development of professional competencies.

The results of the study made it possible to identify the following advantages of e-learning tools:

- individualization of education;
- increased activity of independent work of students;
- increased efficiency of practical exercises;
- expansion of opportunities for using educational resources;
- development of professional problem-solving skills;
- formation of digital competencies.

At the same time, some problems were also observed during the study. In particular, it was found that the insufficient formation of skills of some students and teachers in working with digital technologies, low Internet speed, and license restrictions of some virtual laboratory programs prevent the full use of e-learning tools. The discussions revealed that the use of e-learning tools is not limited to the introduction of technological tools, but is also closely linked to the pedagogical skills, digital competence and methodological training of teachers. The effectiveness of e-learning tools depends on the level of their targeted and systematic use.

CONCLUSION

Developing the professional competence of future engineers based on electronic learning tools is one of the priority areas of the modern higher education system. The rapid development of digital technologies, automation of production processes, and the growing demand for highly qualified engineers in the labor market require the introduction of innovative approaches to the educational process. In this regard, electronic learning tools are emerging as an effective means of improving students' professional training, developing independent educational activities, and forming modern professional competencies. The results of theoretical analyses and experimental studies conducted during the study confirmed that the use of electronic learning

tools has a positive impact on the development of professional competence of future engineers. In particular, it was found that the use of Moodle, Google Classroom, virtual laboratories, electronic textbooks, video lessons, and engineering software tools significantly improve students' professional knowledge, practical skills, information and communication competencies, and independent work skills. The use of electronic learning tools is also important in that it ensures the flexibility of the educational process, creates the opportunity for students to form an individual educational trajectory, and increases the efficiency of using educational resources. This creates a favorable pedagogical environment for implementing a competency-based approach in modern engineering education. Therefore, it is important to further improve the electronic learning environment, widely introduce modern virtual laboratories and simulation programs, and systematically increase the digital competence of professors and teachers.

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